

José F Papí

Crowd-sourced mobility: changing mobility paradigms

The shared economy is in the process of evolving into a significant element of the economic cycle, if it is not already. The idea of sharing things and using them together has worked perfectly well for hundreds of years. All of a sudden it has begun to spawn disruptive business models with spiralling customer numbers and revenues to match (Uber, Airbnb, etc).

Shared (or crowd-sourced) mobility is arguably the most rapidly growing and evolving sector of the shared economy. When it comes to this kind of mobility, transport authorities, centralised thinking and the 'traditional' transport planning can do only little. Citizens must step in and fill in the gaps at neighbourhood level by co-creating solutions. There are already enough assets to work with: existing private and commercial vehicles, transportation grid, tracking and measurement capabilities, smart devices, and so on.

Without additional investment in physical assets, and without adding more vehicles to the streets, it is certainly possible to 'kick start' circular economy through sharing and collaborative solutions. These solutions allow changing urban metabolism by concatenating four fundamental 'sharing' solutions: Ride Sharing, Crowd-Parking, Door-to-Door Urban Freight and Bike Sharing.

Mobility has been massively disrupted (in a positive manner) by mobile apps that today are allowing an optimised utilisation of both transport means – public and private – and infrastructures. Young professionals living in cities increasingly invest in smartphones to hail a ride rather than in their own set of wheels.

Yet this new paradigm is not limited to young people though. Mobile applications now account for more than half (52 per cent) of all the time spent on online digital media. Global mobile app revenues are expected to grow to US\$76.52 billion in 2017. In addition, mobiles (vertical screens) are gaining ground steadily since 2010.

Several of these mobile innovations can be commercially viable, sustainable and backed by investors, not just by government. Nonetheless, there is still a gap between solutions brought by people and the 'commercial reality'. This gap is like an underwater passage most great innovations fail to cross.

Crowd-sourced mobility must start by connecting innovations to lead users at the neighbourhood level. The quality of these connections determines the success

of innovations. Furthermore, such connections must be made early on so that critical inputs for product refinements and diffusion channels can come in like refreshing blasts of fresh air. Delays in such connections are the main reason many good solutions do not survive. Early adoption by lead users brings necessary know-how to improve the solutions and helps identify the distribution channels. In the absence of these channels, investors do not finance the commercialisation of innovative solutions. This is why the connections to lead users are the oxygen lines for innovations; without them, innovations do not receive momentum and funding, and do not last very long.

'Traditional' logistics require centralised planning and thinking; much research has been performed on learning from ant colony and beehive analysis in order to create learning systems. Yet there is a limit on how much we can learn from ants and bees. It is better to design the systems to help people interact in better and smarter manner. This is the philosophy behind crowd-sourced mobility.

Crowd-sourcing and shared-economy ideas are turbo-charged by new technologies. With the proper solutions, such technologies can provide for the European way of bridging social capital and citizen power with the valuable aspects of free market economics. Crowd-sourcing presents economic sense and brings democratic thinking and environmental conscience while at the same time being financially sustainable.

So it seems there is a landscape of new beginnings. We just have to share them.

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